

ACCESSIBLE TOURISM FOR PEOPLE WITH DEMENTIA: AN EVIDENCE-BASED DESIGN APPROACH TO SENSORY GARDENS IN URBAN AREAS

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ABSTRACT: *It is estimated that approximately 55 million people worldwide live with dementia, and this number is projected to triple by 2050. In Brazil and Latin America, cases are expected to increase by 200%, making dementia the seventh leading cause of death globally. Accessible Tourism (AT) for people with dementia, especially through the creation of sensory gardens in urban areas, emerges as a promising strategy to significantly improve the quality of life of these people, while promoting social inclusion, collective well-being and the sustainable development of tourism. Dementia causes cognitive and sensory impairment, resulting in difficulties in perceiving stimuli, disorientation and increased anxiety. In view of this, the aim is to investigate the most recent scientific evidence that, combined with the concept of accessible tourism in urban areas, can guide urban planning managers to promote improvements in city infrastructure and adapt public policies aimed at serving people with dementia. This exploratory research is based on an integrative literature review, including publications between 2020 and 2024, on the themes of "dementia", "tourism", "evidence-based design" and "accessibility in urban areas". As a result, seven elements were considered promising in urban design: (i) controlled stimulation of the senses; (ii) familiarizing and safe environments; (iii) integration of memories and narratives; (iv) variety of accessible routes; (v) incorporation of restorative nature; (vi) appropriate colors and materials; and (vii) connectivity and access to urban transport modes. These elements prove to be effective both accessible and sustainable tourism, promoting inclusive, healthy and economically viable environments.*

KEYWORDS: *dementia, tourism, evidence-based design, accessibility, urban areas.*

INTRODUCTION

The Alzheimer's Disease International (ADI) 2024 report highlighted that more than 55 million people worldwide live with dementia, and someone is diagnosed with the condition every 3 seconds. The global prevalence is estimated to reach 153 million by 2050, a significant increase, particularly in Latin America, where cases are expected to grow by 200% by then, in contrast to the 100% expected in the United States (AID, 2024). Dementia, already the seventh leading cause of death globally and the leading cause in some countries, represents an annual

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economic burden of US\$1.3 trillion, a figure that is expected to more than double by 2030. The responsibility for addressing this challenge lies with governments, which must promote awareness, diagnosis and detection, in line with the goals of the WHO Global Action Plan on Dementia. Currently, only around 50 countries have implemented National Dementia Plans, despite more than 21% of governments having committed to developing them in 2017, reflecting the urgency of a more effective response (AID, 2024).

This set of symptoms that significantly affect the ability to carry out daily activities, predominantly associated with aging, causes symptoms such as memory loss, confusion, depression, apathy and mood swings, in addition to impacting their families, caregivers and society in general. Given the prevalence and severity of this condition, academics have investigated ways to create dementia-friendly communities and provide care for these people (AID, 2024). Studies highlight the importance of providing social comfort, health interactions that preserve the dignity of patients, music-based therapies as a treatment, challenges faced by caregivers and factors that influence the acceptance of psychosocial interventions by patients (Alzheimer's Association, 2024).

According to Buckley (2022), tourism activities have demonstrated benefits for the well-being and mental health of the general population. Despite the potential of tourism to benefit people with dementia and other stakeholders, such as formal and informal caregivers and medical specialists, the topic is still little explored (Waby, 2023). However, tourism has been proposed as a non-pharmacological intervention for individuals in the early stages of dementia (Wen *et al.*, 2022). With dementia still incurable and attempts at new drugs for Alzheimer's Disease (AD) having a failure rate of 99.6% between 2002 and 2012, innovations and cost-effective interventions are becoming increasingly necessary. Accessible Tourism (AT) has the potential to offer experiences that stimulate confidence, memories and independence for these patients (Cummings *et al.*, 2021).

Experts in geriatric care note that most tourism destinations still do not accommodate the unique needs of visitors with dementia. This scenario is slowly changing in countries such as Australia, Canada, the United Kingdom and the United States, where dementia-friendly travel guides are being developed and dementia-specific attractions are being designed, including dedicated cafes, sensory trails and art workshops (Wen *et al.*, 2022). With regard to sensory enrichment, the emerging field of study of Accessible Tourism (AT) presents itself as a promising possibility to be developed, given the character of creating environments that allow all people, regardless of their physical, sensory or cognitive abilities, to fully participate in

tourism activities (Escuderos, Andreu and Ros, 2021).

The World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC) report estimates that the accessible tourism market could reach more than 8 trillion dollars annually (WTTC, 2023). According to the European Network for Accessible Tourism (ENAT), tourists with physical or cognitive limitations, such as people with dementia, tend to travel more frequently and stay for longer periods compared to the average tourist. They often travel with family members or carers, increasing the total number of travelers in a group and therefore increasing direct spending on accommodation, food and activities (ENAT, 2023). Furthermore, the study carried out by VisitEngland in 2018 found that tourists with disabilities or reduced mobility, including those with marked cognitive decline, spent approximately £15.3 billion in the UK during the year. This study emphasizes that tourists who require more specific support have a significant economic impact, especially in sectors such as hospitality and services, and that investment in accessible infrastructure can further attract this audience (Wen *et al.*, 2023).

From this perspective, taking into account the proposal of Accessible Tourism (AT), this study aims to investigate the bibliographic production focused on the applicability of sensory garden projects in urban areas, taking into account: the accessibility of the project; the tourist activity as a proposal for health and well-being for the public with dementia, caregivers, family members and health professionals; evidence-based design (EBD); and the integration of this therapeutic area with the city design. It is expected that the findings of the study can guide urban planning managers to promote improvements in the infrastructure of cities and to adapt public policies aimed at serving people with dementia.

METHODOLOGY

As this is exploratory research, an integrative literature review was used as a method between 2020 and 2024. The research focuses on the theme of "Accessible Tourism of Sensory Gardens for people with dementia in urban areas", guided by the question "How can accessible tourism in sensory gardens benefit people with dementia, caregivers and family members in the urban environment?". The keywords "dementia", "sensory garden", "tourism", "evidence-based design", and "accessibility in urban areas" were defined. The Boolean operator selected was "AND". In this way, it was possible to arrive at the groups: "dementia" AND "sensory gardens"; "evidence-based design" AND "accessibility in urban areas"; "dementia AND "tourism" AND "sensory garden"; "accessibility in urban areas" AND "tourism" AND "sensory garden"; "dementia" AND "evidence-based design".

The searches were carried out between June and September 2024, in the CAPES Periodicals repository. The inclusion criterion adopted was articles whose theme involved the biopsychosocial and therapeutic benefits of sensory gardens for the public with dementia, family members and caregivers. As an exclusion criterion, articles that did not meet the requirements were eliminated: a) language: English; b) search for articles; c) period: last four years (2020-2024); d) filtered by peers; e) exclusion of repeated publications. Of the 534 studies searched, only 12 met the proposal linked to the initial research question. As results, seven promising elements stand out for the design of sensory gardens that are essentially accessible and capable of providing well-being, sensory stimulation and mental health to users, whether they are diagnosed with dementia or not: (i) controlled stimulation of the senses; (ii) familiar and safe environments; (iii) integration of memories and narratives; (iv) variety of accessible routes; (v) incorporation of restorative nature; (vi) appropriate colors and materials; and (vii) connectivity and access to urban transport modes.

RESULTS

As a result of the method adopted, sensory gardens are spaces intentionally designed to engage the five human senses — sight, hearing, smell, touch, and taste — through essentially natural elements. These gardens play a significant role in sensory stimulation, especially for individuals facing cognitive and sensory declines due to neurodegenerative conditions, in addition to providing inclusion and socialization for older people who find themselves isolated in their homes most of the time, deprived of multiple senses essential for healthy aging (Hung *et al.*, 2023). These environments promote positive responses in the brain, helping to improve cognition, memory, and mood. In the context of individuals with dementia, sensory stimulation through contact with textures, aromas, sounds and colors can evoke past memories and provide emotional comfort, alleviating symptoms such as anxiety and agitation (Moszkowicz, Moszkowicz and Porada, 2023).

Studies have shown that integrating these therapeutic environments into urban areas represents a crucial opportunity to improve the quality of life of people with dementia, while transforming these spaces into accessible and inclusive destinations (Fleming, Bennett and Zeisel, 2022; Elbasyoni and Gammaz, 2023). One of the main approaches is to create places that can be easily accessed, ensuring that the urban route to the garden is intuitive and safe (Lak *et al.*, 2021). This can be achieved through fluid connections with public transport and adjacent streets, as well as adequate signage to guide people with cognitive impairments. The *Dementia-*

inclusive Planning and Design Guideline is the first document of its kind to compile strategies and actions for the design of the built environment at the neighborhood scale (Happy Cities, 2023). Even though it does not prioritize sensory garden design, the document presented significant advances in this area of study of urban planning and dementia.

Sensory gardens, when designed for Environmental Enrichment (EE)¹, play a crucial role in stimulating several brain areas, promoting neuroplasticity² and strengthening cognitive reserve³, especially in individuals with dementia and neurodegenerative diseases (Murroni *et al.*, 2021). Neuroscience has shown that exposure to environments rich in sensory stimuli can activate adaptive processes in the brain, mitigating dysfunctional behaviors and slowing synaptic degeneration (Lai *et al.*, 2023). With a view to guiding urban planning managers to promote improvements in city infrastructure and to adapt public policies aimed at accessibility, inclusion and dignity of people with dementia, seven EBD-oriented guidelines were proposed for sensory garden projects, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Proposal Sensory Garden Projects for the Accessible Tourism in urban areas.

(i) Controlled Stimulation of the Senses	
<p>Sensory gardens should balance sensory stimulation without causing overload. According to Attention Restoration Theory (ART), natural environments promote cognitive recovery by reducing the need for directed attention (Olszewska-Guizzo, 2023).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Aromatic plants such as sage (<i>Salvia officinalis</i>), lavender (<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>) and rosemary (<i>Salvia rosmarinus</i>) have demonstrated anxiolytic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant and neuroprotective effects. They have also demonstrated potential in the treatment of common neurological disorders, including Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, migraines and cognitive impairments. They are able to stimulate olfactory memory without overloading the sensory system (Faridzadeh <i>et al.</i>, 2022). . Natural sound elements, such as running water, which create a relaxing ambient sound and help reduce agitation (Cheng and Sabran, 2022). . Varying tactile surfaces, such as different floor textures and plants, which encourage touch and promote reconnection with the environment, improving mood.

¹ Refers to environments that offer a wide variety of sensory, cognitive, motor and social stimuli that can promote brain development and mental well-being. These environments are characterized by the presence of varied visual, auditory and tactile stimuli, opportunities for problem-solving, cognitive challenges and the practice of physical activities (Murroni *et al.*, 2021).

² The brain's ability to reorganize itself and adapt to changes throughout life. This includes the formation of new neuronal connections (synapses), the modification of the strength of these connections and, in some cases, even the generation of new neurons (neurogenesis). This process occurs in response to new experiences, environmental stimuli, injuries or changes in functional demands (Murroni *et al.*, 2021).

³ It refers to the brain's ability to resist neuropathological damage and maintain cognitive function in the face of injury or aging (Lai *et al.*, 2023).

(ii) Familiar and Safe Environments	
For people with dementia, familiar and predictable environments are essential to reduce disorientation and anxiety. Studies show that accessible urban design should minimize physical and cognitive barriers (Fleming, Bennett and Zeisel, 2022).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Well-defined and legible spaces, without confusing passages or unnecessary forks, using visual reference points such as characteristic trees or sculptures. . Clear signage with simple, large icons, aiding spatial orientation and reducing the risk of disorientation. . Soft, uniform lighting, avoiding harsh shadows that could confuse or cause fear. Adequate night lighting also ensures safety.
(iii) Integration of Memories and Narratives	
Sensory garden designs should be able to activate positive memories and promote personal narratives. Studies on affective memory suggest that environmental stimuli can trigger old memories, improving self-esteem and emotional well-being in people with dementia (Fleming, Bennett and Zeisel, 2022).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Create themed areas inspired by cultural or regional memories, such as gardens of local plants, which refer to familiar activities. . Incorporate social spaces that facilitate interaction and social reconnection, with comfortable and accessible furniture for rest.
(iv) Variety of Accessible Routes	
People with dementia and their caregivers have different levels of mobility and endurance. Inclusive pathways should meet a variety of needs, based on the concept of universal design (Fleming, Bennett and Zeisel, 2022).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Routes with accessible, flat and non-slip pavements, which allow wheelchair mobility and prevent falls. . Short and long route options, allowing users to choose their own route according to their level of comfort and need.
(v) Incorporation of Restorative Nature	
Green environments have a proven restorative function in scientific literature. The presence of vegetation improves air quality and provides calming effects (Olszewska-Guizzo, 2023).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Compact urban forests or sensory groves, where the visitor is enveloped in tall vegetation, creating a sense of refuge and privacy. . Water features, such as small ponds or fountains, which not only contribute to the relaxing soundscape, but also serve as visual focal points that anchor the space.
(vi) Suitable Colors and Materials	
The perception of colors and contrasts is altered in people with dementia, and inappropriate use of colors can increase confusion. Soft colors and well-distributed contrasts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Soft, natural colors for main areas, avoiding bright or complex tones that can generate anxiety. . Natural materials, such as wood and stone, create a pleasant tactile connection and do not cause artificial sensations or discomfort to the touch.

<p>help with spatial perception, contributing to walkability and the performance of daily activities (Wiener and Pazzaglia, 2021).</p>	
<p>(vii) Connectivity and Access to Urban Transport Modes</p>	
<p>Sensory gardens should not be isolated enclaves; they should be connected to the city, favoring accessibility and shared use by the entire population. The theory of the walkable city argues that accessible and well-connected environments encourage everyday use of these spaces (Olszewska-Guizzo, 2023).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> . Central location or in areas easily accessible by public transport, increasing accessibility and frequent use by people with reduced mobility. . Smooth transitions between urban areas and the garden, such as green squares that gradually introduce the visitor to sensory immersion.

DISCUSSION

Gradually, partnerships between universities and urban planners have been incorporating sensory garden practices in strategic locations in urban centers, considering people with dementia, residents of the region and, consequently, encouraging tourist visits by the public interested in mental health and cognitively beneficial stimuli for human aging. A practical example of this integration is the *Dementia-Friendly Community Gardens* in Singapore, where sensory gardens were incorporated into densely populated neighborhoods. The planning of these gardens aims to create environments that promote social interaction and engagement with nature, with specific areas dedicated to horticultural activities, sensory stimulation and relaxation (Alzheimer’s Association, 2024). In France, the University of Sorbonne carried out practical applications of sensory gardens mediated by the principles of EE, finding promising improvements in the behavioral and attentional state of elderly people with mild and moderate dementia (Bourdon and Belmin, 2021).

In Australia, more than 20 venues host events in *memory cafes* where people with dementia socialize over morning tea. Similarly, the Museum of Contemporary Art Australia in Sydney offers workshops where educators guide participants through the interpretation of artworks, followed by creative activities to do at home, providing beneficial behavioral stimuli while also making tourism accessible to new participants (Wen *et al.*, 2022). A particularly notable initiative is *Australia’s first dementia-friendly sensory trail*, which opened in 2021 in Woookarung Regional Park, near Melbourne. Designed by the Victorian State Government with input from people with dementia and their caregivers, the nearly one-kilometer trail winds through lush forest inhabited by kangaroos and wallabies. The trail is accessible to wheelchair

users and assistance dogs, with nine designated stops, including community meeting spaces where visitors can listen to music and share their impressions of the natural landscape (Wen *et al.*, 2022).

In the United Kingdom, a *Guide to Dementia-Friendly Tourism*, published by government agencies Visit England and Visit Scotland, outlines strategies for improving services for travelers with dementia. Recommendations include accessible toilets, clear signage, discounts for carers and directories of local attractions suitable for this group. In addition, a growing number of tourist attractions in these countries are implementing dementia-friendly initiatives. The Museum of Modern Art in New York, for example, is developing art appreciation programmes specifically for visitors with dementia. In the United States, more than a dozen museums, galleries, and nature centers in states including Minnesota, Michigan, Tennessee, and others participate in the *Spark! cultural program*, which offers creative workshops for individuals with dementia. Similarly, the National Museums of Liverpool in England offers a variety of services, including guided tours called *memory walks* through the city’s historic sites, group reminiscence sessions, and intergenerational activities for children and their grandparents (Alzheimer’s Association, 2024).

These examples highlight the growing recognition of the need for tourism that caters to people with dementia. While there is still much to be done to expand accessibility, the development of dementia-friendly travel experiences shows promising potential not only to improve the well-being of people affected, but also to create inclusive and enriching experiences that benefit travelers, their caregivers and the community at large. Finally, despite their recognized importance in academic and practical terms in some regions of the world, there is still a lack of studies investigating the implementation and dynamics of sensory gardens in *macromobility*¹ and *micromobility*² of urban modes in order to add data and evidence-based design to urban planners in cities.

¹ Refers to transportation systems that allow travel over longer distances, often intercity or interstate, with greater passenger and/or cargo capacity. These modes are designed to connect large urban areas or even different regions, states or countries, offering medium to long-distance travel (Olabi *et al.*, 2023).

² It involves transportation modes aimed at short distances, typically within urban or metropolitan areas. These means are generally individual or have limited capacity, focused on fast and affordable trips for short distances, such as the last kilometer between public transport and the final destination (Olabi *et al.*, 2023).

CONCLUSIONS

Integrating the concepts of reason, emotion, behavior, and memory into the design of sensory gardens in urban areas not only mitigates the negative impacts of dementia, but also transforms these spaces into tourist attractions with therapeutic benefits. The design principles for sensory garden projects, based on neuroscientific evidence and linked to the purposes of Accessible Tourism, support the emotional and cognitive well-being of people with dementia, creating restorative environments that benefit both patients and their caregivers and family members. In addition, such spaces can stand out as innovative tourist destinations by providing multisensory experiences that encourage relaxation and connection with nature, attracting tourists in search of regenerative and healthy experiences. In addition to welcoming people with dementia, sensory gardens offer other visitors an opportunity to enjoy a space designed to evoke calm, stimulate the senses, and promote emotional recovery. In this way, these environments not only meet the needs of a specific group, but also consolidate themselves as places of reconnection with the natural environment in the midst of urban areas, contributing to the development of inclusive and sustainable tourism, while reinforcing the role of cities as promoters of health and well-being.

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